

Formidlingsaktivitet

Art:	MuonLab: presentation/lecture & labtour.
Sted:	SDU / FKF.
Skole:	Vestfyns Gymnasium, Glamsbjerg.
Dato:	21. november 2024.
Tid:	10:00 – 12:00.
Antal elever:	ca. 10
GDPR / pictures for public?	Yes. Permission obtained.
Lærerkontakt:	Kasper Solberg Hansen
Formidler:	Eike Ravensburg (Syddansk Universitet, FKF / CP3).

Pictures show the muonLab and University students, not the visiting high-school students (no photos were taken during the visit)